

Review form

Impulse funding Open Science Communities-NL

Reviewer 2:

Concrete and realistic project plan

Please elaborate if the project plan is sufficiently concrete and realistic to achieve the intended four objectives 1) networking, 2) knowledge management, 3) increasing visibility and findability and 4) organisational embedding and perpetuation of OSC-NL after the project period.

This evaluation criterion refers to the application as a whole.

The project plan in the proposal is very concrete and detailed, with careful assignment of responsibilities within the team and clear deliverables aimed at achieving each of the four objectives. The schedule described for the projects within each work package seems also sufficiently clear. The only bit of uncertainty, as the proposal notes, is that developments in open science as a whole are unpredictable, and thus planning becomes more challenging as one looks further into the future. As a result, the overall project plan is weighted toward activities in the first two years of the project. It is not entirely clear to me whether the team will have an adequate number of person-months available in those first two years to maintain this schedule, but there appears to be sufficient flexibility in the second half of the project timeline to accommodate that work. The work packages seem to me comprehensive and the deliverables compelling.

Team composition

Please assess if the team composition described in the application in your opinion is appropriate for carrying out the work of OSC-NL.

The team members seem to me highly qualified for and committed to carrying out the work of the proposed executive team. I would like to know a bit more about how the executive team members will coordinate with one another, especially in the case of co-led work packages, or where changes in direction might be required. My assumption is that they are a collaborative team of equals, and that therefore they will develop a set of guidelines and principles for shared leadership and decision making. My only concern is that developing those principles will also take time, and might well benefit from being built into the project itself. Similarly, I'd like to know a little more about the planned relationship between the executive team and the board. How will the team report on its work, and how will the board review and guide that work? Most importantly, what will happen in the case of differences of opinion? Having an agreement between the parties that will guide conflict resolution in advance of such potential conflicts may be advisable.

I am also curious whether Fijten will remain a board member during the course of the project, and whether there are any potentials for conflicts of interest between the team's work on the executive and their employers of record.

Relevant target groups and resources

To what extent are relevant target groups and resources described in the application form? Are the resources appropriate to reach these target groups?

This evaluation criterion refers to the description of reaching the goal “Increase visibility and findability of local Open Science Communities and open science expertise” in the application form. Here the applicant is asked to describe target groups the network currently addresses, and which target groups may still be missing, as well as specifying which communication channels (such as website, newsletters, events, etc.) are already available to the network now and which need to be (further) developed.

The openness of Open Science requires both internal visibility and findability – allowing researchers within the network to collaborate, share work with one another, and build on the collective knowledge so created – and external visibility and findability. That external accessibility requires making the work done within the network available and legible to communities of interest outside traditional university and research structures. The plans for the former seem to me quite strong, as they are built into the structure of the network’s communication channels and governance processes. The plans for the latter are less well developed at this point, depending heavily on social media for communicating beyond the network. Given the highly fractured state of today’s social media landscape, the executive team may find themselves needing to do some investigation and even invention to figure out the best means of reaching both the researchers who are not yet part of the Open Science movement and the broader communities who might benefit from the work shared within the OSC network.

Organisational embedding and sustainability

Please comment if the organisational embedding is sufficiently appropriate for the project plan. Does the application describe realistic steps to perpetuate the network? Note, that the applicant is asked to describe how OSC-NL is (or can be) built up organisationally (type of governance) and which steps OSC-NL could take to perpetuate the network after the end of the project period. At this stage the applicant is not asked for a definite answer. Steps towards sustainability are part of the annual reporting to Open Science NL.

This evaluation criterion refers to the ‘Organisational embedding and perpetuation of OSC-NL after the project period (sustainability)’ section of application form.

I am delighted that part of the work proposed in this project is focused on making OSC-NL sustainable. I strongly suspect that the work of the executive team will prove crucial to OSC-NL’s continued success, even if in a smaller capacity, and thus ensuring that such work is able to continue will be vital. I am not certain from the proposal what models for sustainability will be tested (such as reliance on grant funding, establishing institutional membership fees, or other mechanisms), nor am I clear on the extent to which the current plan to host the executive team within SURF will be sustainable in the long run. However, I strongly believe that the first two years of work on this project will provide the executive team with important data and experience that will enable them to develop a plan for the network’s continuity during years three and four. For that reason, I believe that the current proposal is appropriate.

Summary of your assessment

Overall evaluation of the application

Please describe if you find the application of sufficient quality to receive funding from Open Science NL. Please note that an application of good-enough quality is seen eligible for funding from Open Science NL and the application does not get the opportunity to re-submit an adjusted application form.

I believe that this proposal is of more than sufficient quality to receive funding from Open Science NL. The work plan is thorough, the team strong, and the deliverables as described are key to ensuring the expansion and development of OSC-NL over the project period. Further, I believe that the Dutch model for Open Science Communities could have a powerful influence internationally in creating a model that other nations and groups might build upon. I am eager to follow the work that the executive team will do across the project period and to learn more from this model.